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Research Article

Preparation And Evaluation Of Herbal Hair Spray

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the formulation and evaluation of an herbal-based hair spray incorporating fenugreek, curry leaves, amla, onion, ginger, mustard, and rosemary. The aim was to develop a natural hair care product with beneficial properties while assessing its performance through a series of tests. The pH of the hair spray was determined to be within the optimal range of 4.5 to 7, indicating suitability for scalp application. Homogeneity testing revealed a lack of uniformity in the formulation, suggesting potential challenges in maintaining a consistent product. The spreadability test demonstrated that the hair spray spread effectively over a surface area of 9-10 cm, while the viscosity test indicated that the product was not viscous, which could impact application characteristics. No irritation was observed in the irritation test, confirming the product's safety for use on the skin. The stability test showed that the hair spray remained stable over a period of 3 months, indicating good shelf-life. The product was also found to be easily spreadable, enhancing user experience. Overall, while the herbal hair spray showed promising results in terms of pH, irritation safety, stability, and spread ability, the issues with homogeneity and viscosity warrant further refinement. Future work will focus on improving these aspects to enhance the overall quality and efficacy of the hair spray.

INTRODUCTION

Hair sprays are popular grooming products used to style and hold hair in place.¹ They are typically formulated with a blend of chemicals and polymers that provide the desired level of fixation and manageability. However, with growing awareness of the potential side effects of synthetic ingredients, there is increasing interest in natural alternatives.²⁻⁴ Herbal hair sprays offer a

promising solution by utilizing plant-based ingredients known for their beneficial properties. These natural formulations aim to provide hair care benefits while avoiding harsh chemicals. Herbal hair spray is a variation of traditional hair spray that incorporates natural ingredients and botanical extracts.⁵ These ingredients are often chosen for their potential benefits to the hair and scalp, such as promoting hair growth, reducing

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dandruff, or providing a soothing effect.⁶⁻⁷ Common ingredients in herbal hair sprays include aloe vera, chamomile, rosemary, and tea tree oil. Unlike conventional hair sprays, herbal hair sprays aim to offer styling benefits while also nourishing the hair and minimizing exposure to synthetic chemicals.⁸⁻⁹ Herbal hair sprays often include ingredients like fenugreek, curry leaves, amla, onion, ginger, mustard, and rosemary, each known for their unique properties:¹⁰⁻¹²

- Fenugreek is valued for its moisturizing and conditioning effects.
- Curry leaves are rich in antioxidants and can help promote hair growth.
- Amla (Indian gooseberry) is known for its high vitamin C content and strengthening properties.
- Onion is reputed for its potential to stimulate hair follicles and improve circulation.
- Ginger has stimulating properties that may support scalp health.
- Mustard seeds are believed to have nutrients that can improve hair strength and vitality.
- Rosemary is renowned for its ability to enhance circulation and support hair growth.
- By incorporating these ingredients, herbal hair sprays aim to provide a natural and effective alternative to conventional products, offering benefits such as nourishment, growth stimulation, and enhanced hair health without relying on synthetic additives.¹³⁻¹⁴

Advantages of Hair Spray¹⁵⁻¹⁷

- Long-lasting Hold: Hair spray can keep hairstyles in place for extended periods, even in challenging weather conditions.
- Volume and Texture: Some hair sprays add volume and texture to the hair, making it look fuller and more styled.
- Shine: Certain hair sprays impart a glossy finish to the hair, enhancing its appearance.

- Quick and Easy Application: Hair spray is easy to apply and can be used on various hair types and styles.

Disadvantages of Hair Spray¹⁵⁻¹⁷

- Build-up: Frequent use of hair spray can lead to product build-up on the hair and scalp, making the hair feel heavy or sticky.
- Dryness and Damage: Some hair sprays contain alcohol or other harsh ingredients that can dry out the hair, leading to brittleness and potential damage over time.
- Allergic Reactions: Individuals with sensitive skin or allergies may experience reactions to certain ingredients in hair sprays, especially synthetic fragrances or preservatives.
- Environmental Impact: Aerosol hair sprays contribute to air pollution and can have a negative impact on the environment.

Applications of Hair Spray¹⁵⁻¹⁹

- Everyday Styling: Hair spray is commonly used for daily hairstyling to maintain a neat appearance.
- Special Occasions: For events like weddings, parties, or photo shoots, hair spray ensures that elaborate hairstyles stay intact.
- Theatrical and Performance Use: In theater, dance, or other performances, hair spray is used to secure hairstyles that need to withstand movement and lighting.
- Creative Styling: Hair spray is also used in creative hairstyling, such as creating spikes, curls, or other intricate designs.
- Herbal hair sprays, with their natural formulations, are particularly popular among those seeking a more holistic approach to hair care. However, they may offer a lighter hold compared to traditional hair sprays and might require more frequent reapplication.

MATERIAL & METHODS

RAW MATERIALS AUTHENTICATION²⁰

Raw materials purchase from local source. Received materials were evaluated macroscopically and microscopically.

PHYTO-CHEMICAL EVALUATION²⁰⁻²¹

Phytochemical evaluation provides valuable information related types of chemical present in received powder sample.

PREPARATION METHOD OF HERBAL SPRAY

Extraction of all the natural ingredient with standard procedure. After extraction of individual ingredient, take 10 ml extract s ample from each extract material. Mixed extract into volumetric flask and makeup with 100 ml water. Shake for 30 min and transferred into spray bottle.

EVALUATION PARAMETER²²⁻²⁷

pH: The pH meter was calibrate using a ph-7 buffer solution. Then the meter was adjusted with known pH of buffer solution 4 to 9.2. we take the 30 to 40 ml of the herbal hair spray in beaker. The electrode was immersed and pH value was determined from the automatic display of the pH meter.

Homogeneity test:

The sample was placed on the object glass for the homogeneity test. They should not be non-dispersed particles present in a homogenous preparation.

Spread ability test:

The formulation's spread ability was assessed by applying it to transparent micaplastic. After one minute, the diameter of the preparation's distribution was measured.

Phyto-chemical evaluation:

The hair spray is prepared, then performed the various Phyto-chemical test for glycosides, flavonoids, Tannis, Saponin, Carbohydrate etc.

Irritation test:

1-2 ml of formulation was applied on left hand and observed for 2 hrs. for any signs of redness, irritancy and inflammation.

Stability test at room temperature: Stability at room temperature is cheeked by keeping the product at room temperature for 3 months.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Formulation was made up with herbal ingredients with specified quantity was tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Formulation Table

Sr. No	Ingredients	Quantity taken For 100 ml
1	Fenugreek	4 gm
2	Curry leaves	2gm
3	Amla	2gm
4	Onion	1gm
5	Ginger	1gm
6	Mustard	1 gm
7	Rosmary	4gm

Table 2. Formulation steps of herbal spray

Step-1	Step-2
Step-3	Step-4
Step-5	Step-6

1. pH:

pH was checked by pH meter and pH paper which reveal that pH of herbal spray was 6.0-6.2.

Fig. 1 Result of pH test

2. Homogeneity test:

No particles was observed in formulated spray and all materials were homogenously suspended.

Fig. 2 Result of Homogeneity test

3. Spread ability test:

In this test we observed the how much hair spray was spread on scalp.

Fig. 3 Result of Spread ability test

4. Phyto-chemical evaluation:

Phytochemical evaluation are tabulated in Table 2 & Table 3.

Table 3. Phyto-chemical test for ingredients

Test name	Fenugreek	Curry leaves	Amla	Ginger	Onion	Mustard
Glycoside	+	+	-	-	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	-	-	+	-
Saponin	+	-	-	+	-	+
Protein	+	-	-	-	-	+
Tannins	-	-	+	-	-	-
Terpenoides	-	-	-	+	-	-

Table 4. Phyto-chemicals test for hair spray

Sr No.	Phytoconstituents	Observation
1	Glycoside	+
2	Flavonoids	+
3	Saponin	+
4	Protein	+
5	Tannins	+
6	Terpenoides	+

5. Irritation test:

No irritation or redness on skin or any other side effects observed after applying spray.

6. Stability test at room temperature:

Formulated material was highly stable at room temperature.

Table 5 Brief summary of evaluation parameters

Sr. No	Test	Observation
1.	pH	4.5-7
2.	Homogeneity test	No
3.	Spread ability test	9-10cm
4.	Viscosity test	Not viscous
5.	Irritation test	Not irritation
6.	Stability test	3 months
7.	spread ability	Easily spreadable

CONCLUSION

The evaluation of the herbal-based hair spray formulated with fenugreek, curry leaves, amla, onion, ginger, mustard, and rosemary indicates that the product has several favorable attributes. The pH level was within the ideal range for scalp health, and the product did not cause any irritation, affirming its safety for use. Stability testing over a three-month period confirmed the product's durability and effectiveness. Additionally, the hair spray demonstrated good spreadability, making it user-friendly. However, the formulation faced challenges in homogeneity and viscosity, which affected the uniformity and texture of the product.

Addressing these issues is crucial for ensuring consistent application and overall quality. Future development should focus on refining these aspects to enhance the product's performance and user experience. Despite these challenges, the herbal hair spray shows potential as a natural hair care solution, and with further optimization, it could offer a valuable alternative to conventional hair products.

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CONFLICT OF INREST

Author declares no conflict of interest.

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